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Correlation Patterns of Muon Flux with Vertical Atmospheric Profiles: Insights from Monte Carlo Simulations

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Key Points:

- Monte Carlo model using MCNP and radiosonde/NRLMSISE data was developed to predicts altitude-dependent muon flux and energy spectra
- The model captures key atmospheric effects on secondary cosmic rays, including barometric coefficient and seasonal muon flux variations
- The model can link with dosimetry models to assess biological effects of SCR, including DNA damage and long-term health risks

28 **Abstract**

29 The production, attenuation, and absorption of secondary cosmic rays (SCR) are influenced by
30 atmospheric parameters such as air pressure and temperature. To reliably correlate SCR flux
31 measurements with atmospheric ionization driven by energetic particle precipitation (EPP),
32 these dependencies must be quantified. Monte Carlo simulations enable detailed modeling of
33 stochastic interactions between cosmic radiation and atmospheric components, providing a
34 robust framework for analyzing underlying physical processes and predicting SCR flux under
35 varying atmospheric conditions. This study introduces a simulation model based on the Monte
36 Carlo N-Particle (MCNP) code, integrating atmospheric profiles from radiosonde data to model
37 the production, absorption, and attenuation of SCR. The model's accuracy was validated
38 through comparisons with the PHITS-based Analytical Radiation Model in the Atmosphere
39 (PARMA) and experimental ground-based muon count measurements. It was subsequently
40 used to investigate the dependence of muon flux on atmospheric pressure and temperature up
41 to 20 km altitude. Results reveal a complex relationship between muon flux and atmospheric
42 variables, particularly in the troposphere and lower stratosphere, where pressure correlations
43 and barometric coefficients exhibit both positive and negative values depending on altitude.
44 The model provides a valuable tool for investigating interactions between SCR and climate
45 variables such as humidity and cloud coverage. Furthermore, the model can be coupled with
46 dosimetry models to assess the biological effects of SCR, including DNA damage, genomic
47 instability, cellular dysfunction, and long-term health risks like cancer.

48 **Plain Language Summary**

49 High-energy space particles known as cosmic rays strike Earth's atmosphere and produce
50 secondary particles like muons. Temperature and air pressure in particular affect how many of
51 these particles make it to the ground. Using actual weather data from weather balloons, we
52 employed a computer simulation (MCNP) to model the motion of cosmic rays through the
53 atmosphere. In order to test our model, we compared it to both real ground-based muon
54 measurements and other simulations models. The findings demonstrate that the correlation
55 between atmospheric conditions and muon levels varies with altitude and is more intricate
56 than anticipated. While increased atmospheric pressure at ground level leads to reduced muon
57 flux, this correlation shifts with altitude and changes sign above the tropopause. With the use
58 of this model, we can better understand how cosmic rays interact with the atmosphere and
59 investigate how they affect human health and the climate, particularly radiation exposure
60 during air travel.

61 **1 Introduction**

62 Secondary cosmic rays arise from the interactions of primary cosmic rays (PCR)—predominantly
63 high-energy protons from solar and extraterrestrial sources—with Earth's atmosphere. These
64 interactions trigger extensive particle cascades, producing protons, neutrons, electrons, muons,
65 and other subatomic particles (Grieder, 2001; Mironova et al., 2015; Gaisser et al., 2016).
66 Among these, muons are particularly prominent due to their high abundance and penetrating
67 ability. Capable of reaching Earth's surface and even subsurface depths, muons constitute the
68 most readily detectable component of SCR. They are useful across diverse scientific and

69 technological domains, from probing fundamental physics, such as testing quantum
70 chromodynamics models (Albrecht et al., 2022), to practical applications like muon radiography
71 of volcanic structures and muon tomography for nuclear waste monitoring and characterization
72 (Mahon et al., 2019; Thompson et al., 2021; Giammanco, 2022).

73 The high penetrating power of muons, which is due to their small stopping power and the
74 effects of relativistic time dilation (Grieder, 2001; Groom et al., 2001), makes them ideal natural
75 probes for detecting dynamic atmospheric changes over time. Although muons have a rest-
76 frame lifetime of only about 2.2 μs , their velocities near the speed of light extend their
77 observed lifetime in Earth's frame. For example, a 4 GeV muons generated at altitudes of
78 around 15 km can still reach the Earth's surface, as their decay time is dilated by a Lorentz
79 factor $\gamma \approx 39$, allowing them to live long enough—up to $\sim 85 \mu\text{s}$ in the lab frame—to travel the
80 distance. Continuous monitoring of muon flux at various altitudes could provide real-time
81 insights into the thermal structure of the stratosphere, potentially serving as an indicator of
82 events like sudden stratospheric warming (Tramontini et al., 2019).

83 The integration of muon data into atmospheric and climate science could open new pathways
84 for understanding the interplay between cosmic radiation, atmospheric chemistry, and climate
85 variability. Muons, as a proxy for cosmic ray activity, can help quantify the ionization rate in
86 different layers of the atmosphere. The observed fluxes can be integrated into atmospheric
87 models to estimate the production of free radicals, their relation to cosmic events (e.g., solar
88 particle events, geomagnetic storms, etc.) and their impact on ozone chemistry. This approach
89 is being currently explored in the European Partnership on Metrology (EPM) joint research
90 project BIOSPHERE which aims to develop the necessary instrumentation, methods, and
91 measurement infrastructure to assess how the increasing ionization of the atmosphere, caused
92 by extraterrestrial radiation fields (cosmic rays and solar UV radiation) and amplified by
93 anthropogenic emissions, affects the human and ecological health of our planet [EURAMET
94 21GRD02 BIOSPHERE] (<https://euramet-biosphere.eu/index.php/publis>). This collaborative
95 effort among European metrological institutes and scientific organizations focuses on
96 characterizing the relationships between SCR, PCR, Total Ozone Column (TOC), Ultraviolet (UV)
97 radiation, and atmospheric parameters through field measurements. These measurements are
98 facilitated by sophisticated instrumentation, including novel mobile SCR muon and neutron
99 detectors, cutting-edge semiconductor detectors, and LIDAR systems tailored for vertical
100 atmospheric profiling (Kamtchou et al., 2022; Pierrard et al., 2025, Krasniqi et al., 2022).

101 As muons propagate through the atmosphere, their interactions are influenced by the density
102 distribution of the air (e.g., Winant et al., 2023). As a result, ground-based muon flux
103 measurements capture fluctuations in key atmospheric parameters that affect air density,
104 primarily pressure and temperature, whereas humidity and aerosol concentration contribute
105 only marginally (Maghrabi et al., 2023). It's well established that air pressure plays a crucial role
106 in observed muon flux rates (Wissmann et al., 2005). This is because as air pressure increases,
107 the column of air above the detector becomes denser, acting like a shield that reduces the
108 number of muons that can reach the detector. Dealing with the temperature effect on muons is
109 challenging because it depends on how air is spread out at different heights. Higher
110 temperature at high altitudes makes the air expand, causing fewer hadronic interaction of the
111 particles like π^- and K^- mesons which are the major source of the muons, but also makes muons
112 more likely to decay before they're detected (Wissmann et al., 2005; Tramontini et al., 2019).

113 The overall effect of temperature on muons depends on both how temperature changes with
114 altitude and the energy of the muons. Monte Carlo (MC) simulations, which utilize cross-section
115 data and physics-based models of high-energy particle interactions, combined with vertical
116 atmospheric parameters measured by LIDARs or meteorological radiosondes, enable the
117 separation of atmospheric contributions from genuine cosmic-ray signals. This approach is
118 essential for leveraging muons as a reliable tool for studying atmospheric ionization.
119 This paper presents an MCNP model for cosmic ray propagation through the atmosphere,
120 incorporating vertical profiles of pressure and temperature measured by meteorological
121 radiosondes. The model predicts the production and transport of various secondary particles,
122 including muons (both positive and negative), neutrons, protons, electrons, positrons, pions
123 (positive and negative, and neutral), kaons (positive, negative, and neutral), and photons, which
124 play a crucial role in assessing cosmic-ray-induced atmospheric ionization and its impact on
125 atmospheric dynamics. The model was used to decode the pressure effects from the measured
126 muon flux rate during the BIOSPHERE measurement campaign in Brussels (Pierrard et al., 2025).
127 Using the measured pressure and atmospheric profiles over Brussels, the atmospheric effects
128 on the measured muon count rate could be simulated. Additionally, the model was used to
129 simulate time-dependent muon count rates at different altitudes, which were then utilized to
130 determine the barometric coefficient as a function of height. Furthermore, by employing
131 constant pressure and temperature profiles, the dependence of the barometric coefficient on
132 cut-off rigidity was investigated. This paper focuses exclusively on the validation of the model
133 using experimental muon data and well-established principles, while future work will explore
134 atmospheric ionization and the correlation between primary and secondary cosmic ray fluxes.
135 This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the details of the simulation geometry
136 and cosmic source definitions. Section 3 discusses the results, including comparisons with
137 measured muon rates, PARMA simulations (Sato, 2015), and a correlation analysis of muon flux
138 with atmospheric pressure. The barometric coefficient is determined from simulations across
139 different altitudes, with ground-level values benchmarked against experimental data.
140 Additionally, its dependence on varying cutoff rigidities is explored to assess the effects of
141 primary proton spectrum truncation, and the relevance of SCR simulation for biological systems
142 is discussed. Finally, Section 4 concludes the study and gives an outlook to potential future
143 developments.

144 **2 Simulation**

145 **2.1 Atmosphere model**

146 The simulation of atmospheric propagation of incoming cosmic rays and their resulting air
147 showers was carried out using the general-purpose ionization radiation transport code Monte-
148 Carlo N-Particle (MCNP) version 6.1, a tool validated for cosmic ray applications (Goorley et al.,
149 2013; Gregg, 2013; Garrett and Gregg, 2014). The atmosphere has been modeled as a
150 rectangular prism extending from sea level to an altitude of 65 km, with a base area of 2 km x 2
151 km. This prism was divided horizontally into 230 cells to reflect variations in atmospheric
152 conditions, such as density and air composition, see Fig. 1(a).

153 For the simulation of the atmosphere, radiosonde data (vertical temperature and pressure
154 profiles) over Brussels, provided in the open access database maintained by the University of

155 Wyoming's Department of Atmospheric Science Atmospheric Soundings
 156 (<https://weather.uwyo.edu/upperair/sounding.html>) were utilized (Fig. 1(b) shows the
 157 temperature and pressure profiles for three days in January 2024). The data for the selected 33
 158 days were used to calculate vertical air density using the ideal gas law up to 26 km altitude.
 159 Above that height the density values from the Naval Research Laboratory Mass Spectrometer
 160 and Incoherent Scatter Radar (NRLMSISE) model were used, available through NASA's website
 161 (<https://ccmc.gsfc.nasa.gov/models/NRLMSIS~00/#outputs>), tailored to the specific dates and
 162 Brussels' geographical coordinates. The atmospheric data over Brussels was specifically
 163 selected because during the time period from January 2024 until March 2024, the 2nd
 164 BIOSPHERE measurement campaign to identify and quantify the relationship between cosmic
 165 rays, UV radiation and the thickness of the ozone shield was taking place at the urban Brussels
 166 region, where two institutes involved in the project, Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy
 167 (BIRA-IASB) and Royal Meteorological Institute of Belgium (IRM-KMI), are located. This
 168 campaign involved the simultaneous use of numerous optical instruments such as radiometers,
 169 spectrometers and pyranometers for accurate spectral and wavelength-integrated
 170 measurements of solar UV irradiance, providing access to UV biologically effective dose rate
 171 (UV index), total ozone column and aerosol optical depth, as well as mobile detectors for
 172 ground-based secondary cosmic ray measurements (muons and neutrons) (Pierrard et al.,
 173 2025). In addition, the campaign was complemented by balloon soundings for vertical profiles
 174 of atmospheric parameters, ozone concentration and neutron monitoring, provided by the
 175 IRM-KMI, and satellite data on energetic particle fluxes measured by GOES and PROBA-V/EPT,
 176 provided by BIRA-IASB.
 177

178

179 **Figure 1.** (a) MCNP visualization with the particle display mode showing the schematics of geometry of
 180 the atmosphere and distribution of particles. The Pftotzer maximum marks the altitude where the
 181 production of secondary particles reaches its peak. (b) Examples of temperature and pressure
 182 distribution vs. altitude over Brussels taken from the meteorological sounding database
 183 (<https://weather.uwyo.edu/upperair/sounding.html>)

184

185 In the MCNP input file, density profiles for the model's segments were estimated by
186 interpolating values from both the radiosonde measurements and the NRLMSISE model, to
187 ensure matching with the altitudes of the layers in the atmospheric model. At this stage, the
188 atmosphere's composition in the material card was assumed to be uniform across all altitudes,
189 consisting of 75.53% nitrogen, 23.18% oxygen, 1.28% argon, and 0.01% carbon dioxide by
190 weight (carbon dioxide is converted into its elemental composition, carbon and oxygen, in the
191 material card). The simulation of the atmospheric propagation of high-energy cosmic rays and
192 their cascades utilized MCNP's data libraries and physics models, covering particle energies
193 ranging from approximately 0.1 GeV/n to 1000 GeV/n. For neutron- and proton-induced
194 reactions, the extended version of Japanese Evaluated Nuclear Data Library (JENDL) Version 4.0
195 (up to 200 MeV) was chosen, known as JENDL-4.0/HE. For modeling interactions at
196 intermediate and high energies, we employed the intra-nuclear cascade (INC CEM) and the Los
197 Alamos version of the Quark-Gluon String Model (LAQGSM), respectively.
198

199 2.2 Cosmic source definition

200 The most recent MCNP definition of cosmic ray source available in the code includes automatic
201 source normalization, solar modulation, and geomagnetic rigidity cutoff (R_c) of galactic cosmic
202 ray (GCR) spectra (McKinney *et al.*, 2012). The solar modulation potential is integrated into the
203 cosmic ray source and is set to a specific date with the DAT keyword using the parameterized
204 data. The source generates the energy spectrum of protons and alpha particles at 65 km
205 altitude, based on the date and Earth's location. Since protons and alpha particles constitute
206 99% of primary cosmic rays, it is reasonable to assume that only these particles contribute to
207 the generation of secondary cosmic rays. Figure 2 shows the proton spectra for the selected
208 date of January 1st, 2024, which is close to the maximum solar activity of the current solar cycle
209 (designated as Solar Cycle 25), at five different locations in the northern hemisphere, including
210 the cities of Oslo ($R_c \approx 1.4$ GV), Braunschweig ($R_c \approx 2.9$ GV), Brussels ($R_c \approx 3$ GV), Athens ($R_c \approx 8$
211 GV), and Riyadh ($R_c \approx 14$ GV). The figure shows the progressive clipping of the low-energy
212 galactic spectrum as one moves from low R_c (Oslo), where the magnetic field lines are more
213 perpendicular to the Earth's surface, to high R_c (Riyadh), where the field lines are more parallel
214 to the surface, impeding the entry of cosmic rays into the Earth atmosphere compared to the
215 poles.

216

217 **Figure 2.** Proton spectra on January 1st, 2024 at different latitudes showing the effect of cutoff-rigidity
 218 on the primary spectrum.

219 3 Results and discussions

220 3.1 Validation of MCNP simulations

221 In this study, 33 input files were run, each corresponding to the vertical pressure and
 222 temperature profile of a selected day within the 2nd BIOSPHERE campaign (January 2024 to
 223 March 2024). These particular 33 days were chosen due to the notable structures in the
 224 observed muon flux. In all input files, 18 particle types were set in the model card and
 225 simulated for transport. These include: neutrons, photons, protons, deuterons, tritons,
 226 electrons, positrons, muons (μ^- and μ^+), pions (π^+ , π^- , and π^0), kaons (K^+ and K^-), anti-protons,
 227 anti-neutrons, helium-3 nuclei (^3He), alpha particles (^4He), and heavy ions. The fluxes of
 228 neutrons, muons, protons, electrons, alpha particles, pions, and kaons were scored at 24
 229 different altitudes using the flux-over-a-surface tally. The number of source-particle histories
 230 for each of the calculations was 10^9 , which resulted in a relative statistical uncertainty of
 231 $<0.05\%$.

232 This work will focus solely on the validation of the model using muons, taking the barometric
 233 effect as a case study. The barometric effect significantly influences the muon flux observed on
 234 the ground and is crucial for disentangling cosmic effects from atmospheric artifacts. The
 235 current MCNP model was validated using experimental muon data obtained with the PTB's
 236 mobile muon detector DECOS2 during 33 days from January 5th to February 15th, 2024.
 237 DECOS2 is a new version of the PTB reference detector DECOS1 (Krasniqi et al., 2022), consists
 238 of two scintillator-based detection units, each with a 2-dimensional spatially sensitive readout.
 239 Each unit contains two crossed layers, each composed of ten EJ-200 plastic scintillator bars (50
 240 cm long, 5 cm wide and 1 cm thick). This arrangement of scintillator bars, in combination with
 241 quadruple coincidence detection (one for each scintillator layer), enables position-sensitive
 242 detection with a pixel size of 5 cm x 5 cm. The units can be rotated in space and their separation

243 can be adjusted. The variable distance between the two detector units allows for an adjustable
 244 field-of-view (FOV) of the detector. Figure 3 compares the muon flux measured on the Brussels
 245 urban site with one simulated using the MCNP model and vertical atmospheric profiling
 246 parameters over Brussels (radiosonde data). Simulations compare well with the measured data,
 247 with a the reduced c-square (c-square per degree of freedom) $\chi^2_\nu = \sum_i [(O_i - E_i)^2 / (\nu \cdot \sigma_i^2)] \approx$
 248 0.33, with O_i being the measured muon flux, E_i the simulated muon flux, σ_i the uncertainty of
 249 the measured data and ν the degree of freedom ($\nu=33$).

250

251 **Figure 3.** Comparison of the muon flux measured during the 2nd BIOSPHERE measurement campaign in
 252 Brussels with the muon flux calculated with the MCNP model, both fluxes normalized to the maximum
 253 value. The simulation model was fed with vertical atmospheric profiles over Brussels, which were
 254 measured during the campaign with meteorological radiosonde (see Sect. 2.1).
 255

256 Muon spectra simulated using MCNP model were also compared with those from the PHITS-
 257 based Analytical Radiation Model in the Atmosphere (PARMA), which was validated using
 258 multiple sets of experimental data at nearly the same location and altitude (Sato, 2015, 2016).
 259 Figure 4 shows the comparison of muon plus (μ^+) spectra simulated using the MCNP model and
 260 PARMA as implemented in EXcel-based Program for calculating Atmospheric Cosmic-ray
 261 Spectrum (EXPACS) for the selected altitude of 0.2 km and location (cutoff rigidity) at ~ 8 GV.
 262 One can observe the good agreement between the two, although minor discrepancies between
 263 MCNP and PARMA are likely due to the different models employed. In MCNP, the Cascade-
 264 Exciton Model (CEM) physics model is used for intermediate energy interactions, and LAQGSM
 265 for high energy scenarios. Additionally, atmospheric densities and temperatures in MCNP are
 266 derived from actual radiosonde measurements up to an altitude of about 26 km. Above this
 267 altitude, density values from the NRLMSISE model are used. Conversely, in the PARMA model,
 268 densities and temperatures are based on the US Standard Atmosphere 1976. Furthermore,
 269 while PARMA considers Galactic Cosmic Ray (GCR) protons and heavy ions with charges up to
 270 28 (Ni) as source particles, MCNP only accounts for proton and alpha spectra.
 271

272
 273 **Figure 4.** Comparison of the positive muon spectra calculated with MCNP (this study) and PARMA (Sato,
 274 2015), at an altitude of 0.2 km and a cutoff rigidity of 8 GV. In both cases, the muon spectrum at this
 275 altitude peaks at about 4 GeV.

276 3.2 Relative variation of muon flux and energy spectra with altitude

277 In the simulation, the muon flux was scored at 24 height levels, from the ground surface up to a
 278 height of 25 km. The initial altitudes were set to 0 km, 0.1 km, 0.2 km, 0.5 km, 1 km, 3 km, 5 km,
 279 7 km and 10 km, while for the remaining altitudes the step size was varied between 0.8 km and 1
 280 km. All muon flux values presented in this work are normalized to their respective maximum
 281 values to highlight relative variations with altitude, season, and atmospheric conditions. In
 282 figure 5, the values are shown for selected days at various altitudes, alongside the
 283 corresponding vertical atmospheric temperature profiles. Each curve corresponds to a different
 284 day and illustrates the muon flux variation with temperature across altitudes. Starting from an
 285 altitude of about 25 km, the results show the peak at about 15 km, which is known as the
 286 Pfozter maximum (Grieder, 2001). Beyond this point, at lower altitude, absorption and decay of
 287 muons start to take over and the muon flux begins to reduce. Although temperature variations
 288 of up to 10°C occur, the changes in the muon flux are minimal (up to 4%) because the level of
 289 muon production is more or less constant during the time the experiment campaign was
 290 carried out, as shown in Figure 5(a). However, seasonal variations in atmospheric temperature
 291 have a pronounced effect on muon flux in the lower stratosphere and troposphere, as
 292 illustrated in Figure 5(b). This is evident from the comparison of two extreme days, one in
 293 summer (August, 2024) and one in winter (January, 2024), which were implemented in the
 294 same model to assess their impact on the muon flux. This is because, as the temperature of the
 295 atmosphere rises, so does the atmospheric layer that produces muons. This, in turn, means a
 296 longer flight path down to ground level. More muons can then decay before reaching ground
 297 level. Therefore, at ground level, the muon flux in winter is observed to be 3.6 % higher than in
 298 summer, which compares well to the measurements reported by Wissmann, Dangendorf and
 299 Schrewe (2005).

300 Figure 5b also presents muon flux profiles simulated using AtRIS (Atmospheric Radiation
 301 Interaction Simulator; Banjac et al., 2019a,b; Winant et al., 2023), with protons and alpha
 302 particles as primary inputs. The same atmospheric profile used in the MCNP simulations was
 303 applied in AtRIS; however, the atmosphere was extended to 100 km altitude and discretized
 304 into 200 layers, each 500 meters thick. The recommended GEANT-4 physics list for AtRIS was
 305 used (Winant, Pierrard and Botek, 2025). Primary particle energies ranged from 1 MeV to 1
 306 TeV, distributed across 120 energy bins. To compute the muon flux, the galactic cosmic ray
 307 spectrum was derived using the Force Field Approximation, based on the local interstellar
 308 spectrum (LIS) from Herbst et al. (2017), with a modulation potential of $\phi = 820$ MV
 309 corresponding to January 1, 2024. The resulting muon profiles qualitatively agree with those
 310 obtained from the MCNP model for both summer and winter conditions, with minor
 311 quantitative differences (up to 7%) attributable to differing assumptions between the two
 312 simulation approaches.

313

314 **Figure 5.** (a) Variation of the measured atmospheric temperature and simulated muon flux with altitude.
 315 The temperature profiles represent measurement with radiosondes during selected days in winter. (b)
 316 Seasonal (summer and winter) variations in atmospheric temperature and the corresponding
 317 normalized muon flux with altitude. The results of AtRIS for summer and winter profile of 2024 are also
 318 illustrated for comparison.

319

320 The effects of absorption and decay are best illustrated in the muon spectra presented in Fig. 6.
 321 Energy spectra for both positive and negative muons were scored at various altitudes for the
 322 atmospheric profiles over Brussels corresponding to 15 January 2024. The figure demonstrates
 323 a progressive shift in the peak of the muon distribution, from approximately 0.7 GeV at the
 324 Pftzer maximum to around 4 GeV at an altitude of 100 m. This shift is accompanied by a
 325 significant decrease in muon flux, which drops by more than an order of magnitude from 15.2
 326 km to 0.1 km. While muons lose energy as they traverse the atmosphere, the flux at lower
 327 altitudes is dominated by higher-energy muons, which are less likely to decay due to time
 328 dilation effects, allowing them to penetrate deeper into the atmosphere. In contrast, lower-
 329 energy muons are more likely to decay before reaching these altitudes, contributing to the
 330 observed upward shift at higher altitudes. The charge asymmetry in cosmic ray-induced muons
 331 arises because cosmic rays, which are mostly high-energy protons, collide with atmospheric

332 nuclei and preferentially produce more positively charged mesons, pion plus (π^+) and kaon plus
 333 (K^+), than their negative counterparts.

334

335 **Figure 6.** Simulated energy spectra of negative and positive muons scored at four different altitudes.

336

3.3 Correlation analysis

337 The SCR flux measured on the ground is intrinsically linked to the flux and energy spectrum of
 338 primary cosmic radiation (Gaisser et al., 2016). While PCR initiates the production of SCR
 339 through nuclear interactions in the atmosphere, the resulting SCR flux is modulated by
 340 atmospheric parameters such as pressure and temperature, solar activity, and geomagnetic
 341 effects (Grieder, 2001). Although the correlation of SCR flux with these effects is established to
 342 a considerable degree, refining the empirical models relating SCR flux observed on the ground
 343 with atmospheric parameters would enable incorporating real-time atmospheric data to
 344 improve the accuracy of SCR predictions, but also to use SCR fluxes as a data channel for
 345 climate science.

346 Variation in the atmospheric pressure and temperature can cause considerable changes in the
 347 muon flux measured on the ground. To compare measurements taken at different times or
 348 locations, these pressure-induced variations must be accounted for. This will allow separation
 349 of atmospheric effects from the genuine cosmic ray variations such as Forbush decrease or
 350 ground level enhancements. Figure 7 presents the raw muon and neutron count rates
 351 measured during the BIOSPHERE campaign in Brussels using PTB's muon detector DECOS2 and
 352 the neutron monitor in Dourbes, which is part of the Real-time Neutron Monitor Database
 353 (NMDB) (Mavromichalaki et al., 2011), <https://www.nmdb.eu/nest/>. In both cases, a clear
 354 anticorrelation with atmospheric pressure is observed. A pressure decrease of approximately
 355 40 hPa results in an increase of more than 8% in the muon count rate and over 27% in the
 356 neutron count rate. Pressure changes dominate the effect of atmosphere in the measured
 357 muon flux due to their influence on atmospheric density and cosmic ray interaction
 358 probabilities.

359

360 **Figure 7.** Anticorrelation of the SCR flux with atmospheric pressure. (a) Muons measured with DECOS2
 361 during the Brussels measurement campaign and (b) neutrons measured with the neutron monitor in
 362 Dourbes, which is part of the real-time NMDB.

363 Temperature, while less significant, introduces additional variability, especially in the
 364 stratosphere. The temperature dependence of SCR flux is more complex than that of pressure.
 365 An increase in temperature typically lowers the air density. When this happens in the
 366 stratosphere, this leads to the upward expansion of the air and the rise of muon production
 367 layer. Temperature changes in the troposphere, on the other hand, are more related to the
 368 absorption of muons through air density changes and are often intrinsically encoded in the
 369 pressure effects (e.g., during air mass movements). Here we explore only correlation effects
 370 related to pressure.

371 Figure 8 shows the muon flux scored at different altitudes, from 0.1 km to 16 km. Each
 372 simulation data point represents the relative flux rate over Brussels, with atmospheric profiles
 373 (pressure and temperature) from radiosonde measurements taken over the same location.
 374 From the figure it is evident that below 10.5 km, atmospheric pressure is well anticorrelated
 375 with the muon flux, as expected and measured (see Fig. 7). At higher altitudes, however, a
 376 positive correlation appears between atmospheric pressure and muon flux. This relationship is
 377 illustrated in Fig. 9, which displays the Pearson correlation coefficient for muon flux and
 378 atmospheric pressure up to an altitude of 20 km.

379
 380 **Figure 8.** Comparison of simulated muon with atmospheric pressure at different altitudes. Below 10.5
 381 km, the muon flux and pressure exhibit an inverse correlation, whereas above this altitude, they show a
 382 positive correlation, meaning the muon flux rate and pressure follow the same temporal trend.
 383

384
 385 **Figure 9.** Pearson correlation coefficient between atmospheric pressure and muon flux rate, and
 386 barometric coefficient ($\beta_p = (\Delta\dot{\phi}/\dot{\phi})/\Delta p$, with $\dot{\phi}$ being the muon flux rate and Δp being the change in
 387 atmospheric pressure) as a function of altitude.

388 This effect is also reflected in the barometric coefficient which is needed to correct the pressure
 389 effects in the observed muon data. Figure 9 shows also the barometric coefficient as a function
 390 of altitude over Brussels. At ground level, the barometric coefficient is determined to be $\beta_p = (-$
 391 $0.0014 \pm 0.0002) \text{ hPa}^{-1}$, consistent with the empirical value $-0.00145 \text{ hPa}^{-1}$ predicted by the
 392 empirical curve in Mendonça et al. (2019) for a cutoff rigidity of $R_c=3.2 \text{ GV}$ (specific to Brussels).
 393 The dependence on the altitude reflects the dependence of muon flux with altitude (see Fig.

394 5a). Below the Pfozter maximum, the muon flux decreases as atmospheric pressure increases,
 395 indicating a negative correlation. Conversely, around and above the Pfozter maximum, both the
 396 muon flux and atmospheric pressure decrease concurrently.

397 **Figure 10.** Barometric coefficient, β_p , utilizing atmospheric profiles over Brussels, but with variations in
 398 the truncation of the primary cosmic ray spectrum achieved by adjusting the cutoff rigidity.
 399

400 Figure 10 presents the barometric coefficient as a function of altitude for different cutoff
 401 rigidities, which account for the truncation of the primary cosmic ray spectrum due to Earth's
 402 magnetic field. Each simulation point is derived using the same vertical atmospheric profiles as
 403 in Figure 9. The objective is to demonstrate the altitude dependence of the barometric
 404 coefficient by exclusively varying the cutoff rigidity (i.e., truncating the primary cosmic ray
 405 spectrum), without introducing additional atmospheric parameters as degrees of freedom. The
 406 barometric coefficient generally exhibits a slight increase with higher cutoff rigidity (R_c)
 407 (Mendonça et al., 2019). However, for altitudes below the tropopause, the changes in the
 408 barometric coefficient fall within the uncertainties caused by fluctuations in atmospheric
 409 parameters. This behavior could be well related to the fact that all simulations employ the same
 410 vertical profiles of pressure and temperature.

411 3.4 Relevance of SCR simulation for biological systems

412 SCR, including muons, neutrons, and protons are believed to have significant—primarily
 413 detrimental—effects on living organisms, including humans and animals (Atri and Melott,
 414 2014). Exposure to these particles increases the risk of cancer and other health issues due to
 415 their ionizing nature and the complex molecular damage they can inflict on DNA, RNA, proteins,
 416 and lipids. Although cosmic muons on the ground have relatively low LET compared to neutrons
 417 and protons, their high energy and ability to produce secondary particles (e.g., electrons)
 418 enhance their radiobiological potential, contributing to DNA damage (de Groen, 2022).
 419 Research suggests that the pattern of DNA mutations linked to human diseases corresponds
 420 with the expected effects of continuous muon flux, indicating a possible connection between

421 muon-induced DNA damage and processes such as aging, evolution, and disease incidence—
422 particularly during periods of elevated cosmic ray exposure, such as solar events (Pierrard *et al.*,
423 2025) . Furthermore, when muon flux is combined with high-energy protons and other ionizing
424 components—as often occurs during solar particle events—the overall biological impact is
425 amplified, as demonstrated in the recent paper by Glikoudi *et al.* (2025).
426 Therefore, simulating SCR is essential for understanding and predicting their biological impact,
427 particularly during solar particle events when radiation intensities can surge by several orders
428 of magnitude. Because direct measurements during solar events are limited and often
429 unavailable in critical locations (e.g., upper atmosphere, space habitats, or even high-altitude
430 regions), simulations provide a vital tool for estimating radiation dose, particle penetration, and
431 secondary particle production in realistic biological scenarios.

432 **4 Conclusions**

433 A Monte Carlo simulation model for secondary cosmic ray (SCR) propagation through the
434 atmosphere was developed using the MCNP code version 6.1. The model integrates
435 atmospheric pressure and temperature profiles from radiosonde data up to 26 km altitude,
436 with the NRLMSISE model applied for higher altitudes. It accurately predicts muon flux in
437 regions where atmospheric profiling parameters are valid. The muon flux energy spectra
438 produced by the model align well with those from the PHITS-based Analytical Radiation Model
439 in the Atmosphere (PARMA). This study explored muon flux, energy spectra, and their
440 correlation with vertical atmospheric temperatures at various altitudes. The ground level
441 barometric coefficient determined from simulations at a cutoff rigidity of $R_c=3.2$ GV, $\beta_p = (-$
442 $0.0014 \pm 0.0002)$ hPa⁻¹, is consistent with the value reported in the literature (Mendonça *et al.*,
443 2019). The model also correctly predicts the seasonal variations in the muon flux. For example,
444 about 3.6 % more muons are observed on the ground in winter than in summer, which also
445 agrees well with previous experimental observations (Wissman, 2006). The simulations reveal a
446 negative correlation between muon flux and atmospheric pressure below the tropopause
447 (around 10.5 km) and a positive correlation above it. These findings validate the model's ability
448 to capture key phenomena and the complex interplay between temperature and muon flux
449 across different atmospheric layers. By employing accurate source definition and atmospheric
450 profiling parameters, the model effectively distinguishes genuine cosmic ray effects from
451 atmospheric influences. Furthermore, SCR simulations using this approach can be used to
452 support risk assessment and mitigation strategies in aviation, space exploration, and high-
453 altitude living. They also offer a framework for understanding long-term biological
454 consequences of repeated or chronic low-dose exposure, contributing to research in aging,
455 evolution, and disease mechanisms.

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464 **Data Availability Statement**

465 The University of Wyoming sounding archive makes the atmospheric sounding data used in the
466 simulation publicly available (<https://weather.uwyo.edu/upperair/sounding.html>). The data
467 from the Dourbes, neutron monitor are openly accessible via the Neutron Monitor Database of
468 the real-time NMDB. Processed muon flux results, experimental muon count rates gathered
469 during the BIOSPHERE campaign, and the Monte Carlo simulation model are all publicly
470 accessible in Zenodo at: [DOI: to be inserted]. NASA's Community Coordinated Modelling
471 Centre (<https://ccmc.gsfc.nasa.gov/models/NRLMSISE~00>) provided the NRLMSISE-00 model
472 outputs.
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474 **References**

475 Albrecht, J. et al. (2022) 'The Muon Puzzle in cosmic-ray induced air showers and its connection
476 to the Large Hadron Collider', *Astrophysics and Space Science*, 367(3). doi: 10.1007/s10509-
477 022-04054-5.

478 Atri, D. and Melott, A. L. (2014) 'Cosmic rays and terrestrial life: A brief review', *Astroparticle
479 Physics*, 53(C), pp. 186–190. doi: 10.1016/J.ASTROPARTPHYS.2013.03.001.

480 Banjac, S., Herbst, K., and Heber, B. (2019a), 'The atmospheric radiation interaction simulator
481 (AtRIS): Description and validation', *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 124:50–
482 67.
483

484 Banjac, S., Herbst, K., and Heber, B. (2019b), 'On-the-fly calculation of absorbed and
485 equivalentatmospheric radiation dose in a water phantomwith the atmospheric radiation
486 interactionsimulator (AtRIS)', *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 124:50–67.
487

488 Gaisser, T.K., Engel, R. and Resconi, E. (2016) *Cosmic Rays and Particle Physics*. Cambridge
489 University Press. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139192194>.

490 Garrett, E. and Gregg, W. (2014) 'MCNP6 Cosmic & Terrestrial Background Particle Fluxes -
491 Release 4' (No. LA-UR-14-24445). Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL), Los Alamos, NM
492 (United States).

493 Giammanco, A. (2022) 'Muon Imaging: Present Status and Emerging Applications'.

494 Gkikoudi, A. et al. (2025) 'Synergistic Effects of UVB and Ionizing Radiation on Human Non-
495 Malignant Cells: Implications for Ozone Depletion and Secondary Cosmic Radiation Exposure',
496 *Biomolecules*, 15(4), p. 536. doi: 10.3390/BIOM15040536/S1.

- 497 Goorley, J.T. et al. (2013) Initial MCNP6 release overview-MCNP6 version 1.0 (No. LA-UR-13-
498 22934). NM (United States).
- 499 Gregg, W. (2013) 'MCNP Simulations of Background Particle Fluxes from Galactic Cosmic Rays'.
500 In *Transactions of the American Nuclear Society Annual Meeting, Atlanta* (Vol. 108, pp. 651-
501 654).
- 502 Grieder, P. K. F. (2001) 'Cosmic rays at Earth. Elsevier'.
- 503 de Groen, P. C. (2022) 'Muons, mutations, and planetary shielding', *Frontiers in Astronomy and*
504 *Space Sciences*, 9, p. 1067491. doi: 10.3389/FSPAS.2022.1067491/BIBTEX.
- 505 Groom, D. E., Mokhov, N. V. and Striganov, S. I. (2001) 'MUON STOPPING POWER AND RANGE
506 TABLES 10 MeV–100 TeV', *Atomic Data and Nuclear Data Tables*, 78(2), pp. 183–356. doi:
507 10.1006/ADND.2001.0861.
- 508 Herbst, K., Muscheler, R., Heber, B. (2017), 'The new local interstellar spectra and their
509 influence on the production rates of the cosmogenic radionuclides ^{10}Be and ^{14}C ', *J. Geophys.*
510 *Res. Space Phys.* 122, 23–34.
- 511
512 Kamtchou, B. et al. (2022) 'Spectral tracking of energetic charged particles in wide field-of-view
513 with miniaturized telescope MiniPIX Timepix3 1×2 stack', *Journal of Instrumentation* , 17(03),
514 p.C03028. doi: 10.1088/1748-0221/17/03/C03028
- 515 Krasniqi, F. et al. (2022) 'PTB metrological infrastructure for the environmental dose
516 assessment', 132(3), pp. 21–31. Available at: <https://inis.iaea.org/records/pymbr-brs52>
517 (Accessed: 6 May 2025).
- 518 Maghrabi, A. H. et al. (2023) 'The Role of Atmospheric Pressure, Temperature, and Humidity on
519 Cosmic Ray Muons at a Low Latitude Station', *International Journal of Astronomy and*
520 *Astrophysics*, 13(3), pp. 236–258. doi: 10.4236/IJAA.2023.133014.
- 521 Mahon, D. et al. (2019) 'First-of-a-kind muography for nuclear waste characterization'.
522 *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A*. 2019 Jan 28;377(2137):20180048. doi:
523 10.1098/RSTA.2018.0048.
- 524 Mavromichalaki, H. et al. (2011) 'Applications and usage of the real-time Neutron Monitor
525 Database', *Advances in Space Research*, 47(12), pp. 2210–2222. doi:
526 10.1016/J.ASR.2010.02.019.
- 527 McKinney, G. W. et al. (2012) 'MCNP6 Cosmic-Source Option' (No. LA-UR-12-22318). Los
528 Alamos National Laboratory (LANL), Los Alamos, NM (United States).
- 529 Mendonça, R. R. S. et al. (2019) 'Analysis of Cosmic Rays' Atmospheric Effects and Their
530 Relationships to Cutoff Rigidity and Zenith Angle Using Global Muon Detector Network Data'.
531 *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 124(12), pp. 9791–9813. doi:

532 10.1029/2019JA026651.

533 Mironova, I. A. et al. (2015) 'Energetic Particle Influence on the Earth's Atmosphere', *Space*
534 *Science Reviews*, 194(1–4), pp. 1–96. doi: 10.1007/s11214-015-0185-4.

535 Pierrard, V. et al. (2025) 'BIOSPHERE measurement campaign from January 2024 to March 2024
536 and in May 2024: Effects of the solar events on the radiation belts, UV radiation and ozone in
537 the atmosphere', *AIMS Geosciences* 2025 1:117, 11(1), pp. 117–154. doi:
538 10.3934/GEOSCI.2025007.

539 Sato, T. (2015) 'Analytical model for estimating terrestrial cosmic ray fluxes nearly anytime and
540 anywhere in the world: Extension of PARMA/EXPACS', *PLoS ONE*, 10(12), pp. 1–33. doi:
541 10.1371/journal.pone.0144679.

542 Sato, T. (2016) 'Analytical model for estimating the zenith angle dependence of terrestrial
543 cosmic ray fluxes', *PLoS ONE*, 11(8), pp. 1–22. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0160390.

544 Thompson, L. et al. (2021) 'The use of muon radiography in safeguarding geological
545 repositories', *Safety of Nuclear Waste Disposal*, 1, pp. 279–280. doi: 10.5194/sand-1-279-2021.

546 Tramontini, M. et al. (2019) 'Middle-Atmosphere Dynamics Observed With a Portable Muon
547 Detector', *Earth and Space Science*, 6(10), pp. 1865–1876. doi: 10.1029/2019EA000655').

548 Winant M., Pierrard V., Botek E. (2025), Good Practice Guide for the simulation and estimation
549 of particle fluxes during minimum solar activity, maximum solar activity and the recent Solar
550 Energetic Particle Events, www.euramet-biosphere.eu.

551 Winant, A., Pierrard, V., Botek, E. and Herbst, K. (2023) 'The Atmospheric Influence on Cosmic-
552 Ray-Induced Ionization and Absorbed Dose Rates', *Universe*, 9, no. 12, p. 502.
553 doi: 10.3390/universe9120502.

554 Wissmann, F. (2006) 'Variations observed in environmental radiation at ground level', *Radiation*
555 *Protection Dosimetry*, 118, pp. 3–10. doi.org/10.1093/rpd/nci317.

556 Wissmann, F., Dangendorf, V. and Schrewe, U. (2005) 'Radiation exposure at ground level by
557 secondary cosmic radiation', *Radiation Measurements*, 39(1), pp. 95–104. doi:
558 10.1016/J.RADMEAS.2004.03.025.

559